

PLANNING OF AN EXPERIMENT TO DETERMINE THE FORCE PARAMETERS ACTING ON THE CUTTING ELEMENT OF FORM-MILLING CUTTERS FOR KZh20 MACHINE

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Abstract. The article presents the search for an optimal solution to obtain regression models - dependencies of the tangential component of the cutting force P_z on the elements of cutting modes. The research methodology is based on the theory of experimental design, cutting theory and cutting tool.

It has been established that by applying the method of planning a factorial experiment, a regression equation was obtained that makes it possible to adequately describe the dependence of such an objective function as the cutting force P_z on the main influence parameters – cutting depth t , feeding S , and spindle rotational speed n . It is shown that the cutting force P_z is most influenced by the cutting depth t , and the lowest by the feeding S . For example, when the cutting depth is changed in the range $t = 0.1 \div 0.7$ mm, the main component of the cutting force P_z increases by 7.59 times at feeding $S = 1.1$ mm/rev and spindle rotational speed $n=94$ rpm.

The dependencies of planning a factorial experiment in the study of the technological process of restorative repair of the working surface of wheelset on KZh 20 machines have been established. Using the method of planning a factorial experiment, a regression equation was obtained that allows to describe adequately the dependence of the cutting force P_z on the parameters of the cutting modes.

The results of the work can be used to increase efficiency in restoring the shaped profile of the working surface of the bandages and wheelsets of rail transport vehicles without rolling out from under the locomotive.

Keywords: wheelset, parameters of the cutting modes, one-factor studies, cutting force, cutting depth, feeding, speed.

Introduction. Rail transportation of open pit mining plays an important role in the general complex of resource development. Its technical and economic features affect the operation of the entire transportation system. The increase in the number of wheelsets leads to a growth in the volume of repair works and the cost of maintenance